
CHARACTERIZATION OF UREOLYTIC BACTERIA FROM NITROGENOUS WASTE DUMPS IN PORT HARCOURT NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Three nitrogenous dump-sites viz. urinary spots, poultry dung compost and nitrogenous fertilizer storage site, and a non-nitrogenous site (as control) in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State of Nigeria, were characterised for their aerobic ureolytic bacteria isolates. The nitrogenous waste sites compared with the non-nitrogenous site clearly indicated that the TCFU of bacteria was significantly lowered as a result of dumping of all forms of nitrogenous wastes (ANOVA P = 0.019). Tentatively and cumulatively identified 10 randomly isolated aerobic bacterial species from the sites included *Staphylococcus* 5(12.5)*, *Streptococcus* 2(5.0), *Proteus* 8(20.0), *Serratia* 2(5.0), *Flavobacterium* /*Xanthomonas* 3(7.5), *Escherichia coli* 4(10.0), *Klebsiella* /*Enterobacter* 2(5.0) and *Pseudomonas* 4(10.0); *Bacillus* and other Gram-positive rods 10(25.0) were frequently isolated in all the samples. From these isolates, urease activity was more elaborated in the nitrogenous fertilizer dump-site in which three isolates of *Proteus* sp and three of *Pseudomonas* sp elaborated urease activity. While urease activity was also elaborated by *Proteus* (2 isolates) and the *Klebsiella* /*Enterobacter* (one isolate) in the urinary spot only (2 isolates) of *Proteus* elaborated urease activity in the poultry-dung site. It was not clear if there were physiological factors arising from human urine and poultry dung that might have limited the activity *Pseudomonas* sp to the nitrogenous fertilizer only. The probable source of variability in the type of urea degrading bacterial isolated from the sites and the effect of compromising microbiological environmental cleansing capability were discussed.

* Numbers in parenthesis represent percentages.

KEYWORDS: Urea, nitrogenous wastes, degradation, waste-dump, urease.

INTRODUCTION

Nitrogenous waste-dumps

Urea is excreted into soil by animals. In the soil urea is constantly being utilized by microorganisms especially bacteria which break it down into ammonia and carbon dioxide. Other sources of urea into the soil include manure from compost-pit, poultry dung and artificial fertilizer application. Subsequent conversion of ammonia in the soil leads to the formation of nitrates and nitrites which are utilized by plants (Pelczar et al, 1986). Under aerobic conditions urea breakdown is catalyzed by the enzyme urease produced mainly by microorganisms. All nitrogenous waste dumps are characterized by the release of ammonia which constitutes an environmental nuisance. This leads to phytotoxicity, bleaching of soils; exudations of much pungent odour in which eutrophication, characterized by offensive algal blooms occur causing loss of aesthetic values.

Urea as a chemical

Historically, the study of urine and its composition started in the mid-eighteenth century when a number of scientists had drawn attention to the presence of a particular nitrogenous substance in urine. In 1773, F. M. Boveille was the first to extract from urine a compound rich in nitrogen that could be degraded to carbonic acid and ammonia. At the turn of the eighteenth century, A. F. Fourcroy and N. L. Vanquelin obtained crystalline urea on treatment of fresh concentrated urine with nitric acid. This feat represented the transitional phase between organic and inorganic substances as it was the first time an organic compound was produced in the laboratory and hence the first step in modern biochemistry (Lehninger, 1982).

Urea is the diamide of carbonic acid (H₂CO₃); it is alternatively called carbamide. It is a white, crystalline, water-soluble compound, with a melting point of 132.7 °C. It has the chemical formula, H₂N - CO - NH₂; it is

soluble in alcohol but only slightly soluble in ether. Synthesized urea in the body forms the primary excretory product of mammals and other lower animals (Lehninger, 1982). The metabolic pathway for the synthesis of urine is the Ornithine Cycle. In the liver, liberated ammonia (NH₃) combines with carbon dioxide (CO₂) and phosphate (PO₄) to form carbamyl-phosphate; this reacts with the amino acid (Ornithine) to form citrulline. Further reaction of citrulline with aspartic acid forms arginosuccinic acid, which decomposes into arginine. Arginine is broken down into urea and Ornithine (Lehninger, 1982). Each molecule of urea is thus formed from two molecules of ammonia and one of carbon dioxide; involving seven different enzymes.

Microbiological degradation of urea

A number of aerobic bacteria species have the capability to breakdown urea in the soil under aerobic conditions viz. *Proteus*; *Morganella*; *Serratia*; *Pseudomonas*; *Clostridium*; *Fusobacterium*; *Ureaplasma*; *Providencia*; *Sarcina* etc (Cheesbrough, 1991). The rate of urea hydrolysis depends on the rate of urea application, temperature, and soil biochemical status (Overrein and Moe, 1967). Forty anaerobic ureolytic bacteria have been isolated and characterized from the soft faeces and caecal content of rabbit (Cronciani et al, 1984). The isolates include among other species, *Clostridium*; *Peptococcus*; *Peptostreptococcus*; *Peptostreptococcus* and *Fusobacterium*.

This study was therefore carried out to elucidate if there were probable variability arising from the type of urea degrading bacterial from the different nitrogenous dump sites and to indicate if there was compromising of microbiological environmental cleansing capability as a result of dumping of nitrogenous wastes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection

Three different nitrogenous waste dump-sites and a non-nitrogenous site (as control) were selected in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State of Nigeria. The nitrogenous waste dump-sites locations included: a urinary spot at the Faculty of Science, and a poultry dung dump-site; both at the Rivers State University of Science and Technology; and a fertilizer storage site at the Agricultural Development Programme at Rumuodomanya. From each of the dump sites three separate urea contaminated soil samples (two spatulas full each) were collected two feet from the focal centre of the dump into universal bottles using spatula. The bottles and spatulas had earlier been sterilized in the oven at 160 °C for 1 hour.

Experimental procedure

One gram of soil from each of the samples including the control was weighed into a 250 ml conical flask and diluted with 10.0 ml of sterile distilled water. Ten-fold serial dilutions were carried out in which 0.1 ml of the 10⁻⁵ dilution was plated in triplicates on Nutrient Agar plates for Spread Plate Count (SPC) of colony forming bacterial units. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 48 h. Bacterial counts of 30-300 per plate were accepted as statistically correct. Ten morphologically representative isolates were randomly picked from the plates from each of the samples for identification of aerobic bacterial forms. The isolates were stored in sterile universal bottles and preserved at 5 °C in the refrigerator and for sub-culturing, characterization and identification. The samples were encoded as follows: Urinary Spot Dump-Site (USS); Poultry-dung Dump-Site (PDS); Fertilizer Dump-Site (FDS) and Non-nitrogenous Site (NNS).

Identification of bacterial forms

Colony morphological and Gram-stain reactions were used for the preliminary identification of the isolates into the basic bacterial forms. Further identification was carried out using various biochemical tests. These tests include: sugar utilization; H₂S, gas and acid production from Kligler Iron Agar (KIA); Coagulase test (tube/slide), urease activity, catalase production and the utilization of Manitol sugar in Manitol Salt Agar (MSA). Statistical analysis included the One-way Analysis of Variance (Zigma stat 32) on the SPC.

RESULTS

The tentatively identified aerobic bacterial species were characterized as shown in Table 1. The isolates of greatest preponderance were the *Enterobacteriaceae*, followed by the *Micrococcaceae*. The *Enterobacteriaceae* (*Proteus*, *Serratia*, *Flavobacterium* /*Xanthomonas*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella* /*Enterobacter* and *Pseudomonas* spp). The *Micrococcaceae* (viz. *Staphylococcus* and the *Streptococcus* spp) and *Bacillus* and other Gram-positive rods were frequently isolated in all the samples. The USS, was most colonized by the *Flavobacterium* /*Xanthomonas*, followed by the *Proteus* sp and *Bacillus* and other Gram-positive rods.

Table 1: Characterization of bacterial isolates from nitrogenous waste dumps.

Tests & Assessments	Isolates								
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX
Colony Morphology	Entire Creamy	Entire Golden	Wrinkled Dry	Moist Translus	Moist Entire	Mucoid Orange	Moist Creamy	Whitish Slimy	Moist Brownish
Grams' Reaction	G + ve Cocci	G + ve Cocci	G + ve Rod	G – ve Rod	G – ve Rod	G – ve Rod	G – ve Rod	G – ve Rod	G - ve Rod
Growth on MSA	+ ve	- ve	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT
Coagulase Test	+ ve	- ve	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT
Catalase activity	+ ve	- ve	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT
Sugar Utilization - Lactose - Mannose - Glucose - Sucrose	NT	NT	NT	- ve - ve + ve + ve	- ve + ve + ve + ve	NT	+ ve + ve + ve - ve	+ ve + ve + ve + ve	- ve - ve - ve - ve
Growth on KIA - Gas formation - H ₂ S “ - Slope - Butt	NT	NT	NT	+ ve + ve R Y	- ve - ve Y Y	NT	+ ve - ve Y Y	+ ve - ve Y Y	- ve - ve R R
Urease Activity	- ve	- ve	- ve	+ ve	- ve	- ve	- ve	+ ve	+ ve
Tentative Identification	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>Streptoc. Sp</i>	<i>Bacillus Sp</i>	<i>Proteus Sp</i>	<i>Serratia Sp</i>	<i>Flavo/Xant Spp</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Kleb/Ent. Sp</i>	<i>Pseud. Sp</i>
Frequency of Occurrence of Bacteria - USS - PDS - NFS	1 *(10.0) 1 (10.0) 0 (0.0)	1 (10.0) 1 (10.0) 0 (0.0)	2 (20.0) 3 (30.0) 3 (30.0)	2 (20.0) 2 (20.0) 3 (30.0)	1 (10.0) 0 (0.0) 0 (0.0)	3 (30.0) 0 (0.0) 0 (0.0)	0 (0.0) 1 (10.0) 1 (10.0)	0 (0.0) 2 (20.0) 0 (0.0)	0 (0.0) 0 (0.0) 3 (30.0)
Cumulative Frequency of Occurrence of Bacteria	2 (6.7)	2 (6.7)	8 (26.7)	7 (23.3)	1 (3.3)	3 (10.0)	2 (6.7)	2 (6.7)	3 (10.0)
Frequency of Occurrence of Urea degrading Bacteria - USS - PDS - NFS	- ve	- ve	- ve	2 2 3	- ve	- ve	- ve	2 0 0	0 0 3

Urinary Spot Site (USS); Poultry Dung Site (PDS); Nitrogenous Fertilizer Storage Site (NFS). * Numbers in parenthesis represent percentages. NT = Not tested; - ve = Negative; + ve = Positive

The PDS, was more colonized by the *Bacillus* and other Gram-positive rods followed by the *Proteus* sp and the *Klebsiella /Enterobacter*. The NFS was most colonized by the urease degraders viz. *Pseudomonas*, *Proteus* spp and the *Bacillus* and other Gram-positive rods. For the NNS, the *S.aureus* and the *E.coli* spp were the most frequently isolated. The most frequently isolated species which occurred in all the sites were the *Bacillus* and other Gram-negative rods and the *Proteus* spp. The *Micrococcaceae* (viz. *Staphylococcus* and the *Streptococcus* spp) were limited to the urinary, poultry waste and non-nitrogenous sites. Among the *Enterobacteriaceae*, the *Serratia* occurred in the USS and NFS; while the *Flavobacterium/ Xanthomonas* spp occurred only in the human urinary waste site; the *Klebsiella /Enterobacter* was isolated only in the poultry waste and the *Pseudomonas* spp occurred only in the Nitrogenous fertilizer dump.

Fig 1: The TCFU of bacteria for the nitrogenous waste sites. USS = Urinary Spot Dump-Site; PDS = Poultry-dung Dump-Site; FDS = Fertilizer Dump-Site and NFS = Non-nitrogenous Site (ANOVA P = 0.019) (Data = Mean ± SE; n = 3).

From Fig 1, the TCFU of bacteria for the nitrogenous waste sites compared to the non-nitrogenous control site indicated significant variation in which the non-nitrogenous was site was significantly higher in TCFU; values ranging from 1.12E+07 (±1.05E+06) for the PDS to 1.30E+08 (±4.60E+06) for the NNS (ANOVA P = 0.019). Tentatively and cumulatively identified 10 randomly isolated aerobic bacterial species from the sites included *Staphylococcus* 5(12.5), *Streptococcus* 2(5.0), *Proteus* 8(20.0), *Serratia* 2(5.0), *Flavobacterium /Xanthomonas* 3(7.5), *Escherichia coli* 4(10.0), *Klebsiella /Enterobacter* 2(5.0) and *Pseudomonas* 4(10.0); *Bacillus* and other Gram-positive rods 10(25.0) were frequently isolated in all the samples.

Urease activity was most elaborated in the nitrogenous fertilizer followed by the human urinary spot and the poultry dump site as shown in Table 1. Urease activity in the nitrogenous fertilizer appear to be elaborated exclusively by the *Pseudomonas* spp, the *Proteus* sp and *Klebsiella* spp showed activity only in the animal source nitrogenous wastes (viz. Urinary and Poultry nitrogenous wastes). The *Proteus* was the organism of widest range of biodegradation as it elaborated urease activity in all the nitrogenous waste dumps including the control.

DISCUSSION

Apart from the issue of constituting environmental nuisance through eutrophication, the fact that there was a significant decrease in the bacterial population and probably that of other microorganisms implied that indiscriminate dumping of nitrogenous wastes constitutes a very important source of environmental pollution. Factors such as protooperation, syntrophy etc would be affected leading to altered soil fertility, and other far

reaching effects in the micro food web of the dumping site. Indiscriminate urination around premises especially in university campuses and areas of high population densities generally therefore deserve some form of control and legislation.

The isolation of the *Staphylococcus* and the *Streptococcus* spp from the nitrogenous wastes of animal origin (i.e. USS and PDS) and the occurrence of the *Bacillus* and other gram-positive rods in all the samples was not unexpected. While the *Micrococcaceae* are known to be indigenous microflora of animal skins, the *Bacillus* sp are known to be hardy due to their ability to form endospores and derive carbon for their metabolism from a number of complex sources (Madigan et al, 2000).

The indication that urease activity was elaborated in the nitrogenous fertilizer dump site only by *Pseudomonas* sp; appears to indicate that this source which is inorganic was probably less easily degraded or more toxic to bacteria generally than the animal source nitrogenous wastes. With the ever increasing demand for more food worldwide and especially in the Third World, the use of inorganic fertilizer will increase thereby exacerbating environmental problems from this source. For the animal source nitrogenous wastes however, the *Proteus* and *Klebsiella* spp which are of enteric origin prominently elaborated urease activity.

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